

AIMS-TBI - Automated Identification of Moderate-Severe Traumatic Brain Injury Lesions: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

AIMS-TBI - Automated Identification of Moderate-Severe Traumatic Brain Injury Lesions

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

AIMS-TBI

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Moderate to Severe Traumatic Brain Injury (msTBI) is caused by external forces (eg: traffic accidents, falls, sports) causing the brain to move rapidly within the skull, resulting in complex pathophysiological changes. Primary injuries arising from the initial forces (e.g., haematoma, hemorrhages, and contusions)(Mckee & Daneshvar, 2015), subsequently induce a cascade of secondary injuries (e.g., gliosis, encephalomalacia, (Maas et al., 2008)) that can include life threatening disorders such as raised intracranial pressure, requiring acute surgical intervention (Bullock et al., 2006). Each of these primary, secondary and surgery related processes can cause structural deformation in the brain. Each patient with msTBI has a unique accumulation of these structural changes, contributing to extremely heterogeneous lesions, considered a hallmark of msTBI (Covington & Duff, 2021). These lesions differ from other common brain pathologies (stroke, multiple sclerosis (MS), brain tumor) as they can be both focal or diffuse, varying in size, number and laterality, extending through multiple tissue types (e.g., grey matter (GM), white matter (WM), cerebrospinal fluid (CSF)), and can also occur in homologous regions of both hemispheres. Lesions such as these can complicate image registration, normalization, and are known to introduce both local and global errors in brain parcellation (Diamond et al., 2020; King et al., 2020). While several tools exist to compensate for lesions in neuroimaging pre-processing (i.e., the high definition brain extraction tool (HD_Bet) (Isensee et al., 2019), virtual brain grafting (VBG)(Radwan et al., 2021)), most require time consuming manual creation of lesion masks and subsequent manual quality assessment. Furthermore, in our experience, automated methods that have been developed for lesions of different etiologies (e.g. stroke, tumors [Sanjuán et al., 2013]) often underperform in TBI cases.

In the absence of appropriate processing tools, current lesion compensation techniques in msTBI include ignoring the lesions (resulting in unreliable findings), excluding msTBI patients with large lesions (limiting the generalizability), or manual segmentation of lesions prior to analysis (time consuming). Additionally, manual

segmentation is often only feasible in smaller, single-site studies which lack the statistical power to perform subgroup analyses. These restrictive approaches limit the ability to investigate how factors such as type of injury (axonal injury, focal lesions, and diffuse microlesions), severity (mild, moderate, severe), and presence of comorbid injuries or complications (especially those that affect pulmonary and cardiovascular function, see [Crawford et al., 2019] and post-traumatic seizure [Bennett et al., 2017; Liesemer et al., 2011]) impact patient's functional outcomes. To capture this information, msTBI researchers need access to an accurate, automatic lesion segmentation algorithm trained on large multicohort magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) datasets, where images are aggregated across sites. Whilst a handful of TBI specific algorithms exist, they require either multiple image types (Kamnitsas et al., 2017) (T1-weighted, T2-weighted, fluid attenuated inversion recovery image [FLAIR], gradient echo [GE] & proton density [PD]) or can run on only computed tomography [CT] images (Jain et al., 2019). The necessity for multiple image types limits the applicability of such tools to large-scale consortia aggregating common MRI scans across sites.

The AIMS-TBI challenge leverages data shared within the Enhancing NeuroImaging Genetics through Meta-Analysis (ENIGMA) Consortium (Thompson et al., 2022) Traumatic Brain Injury working group, specifically, the Pediatric msTBI and Adult msTBI subgroups. The AIMS-TBI challenge will focus on identifying lesions in T1-weighted (T1w) MRI data only as it is both the most common MRI scan across our ENIGMA TBI consortium and exhibits less parameter variation (e.g. 1 mm³ voxel size was relatively common in our previous published work, Dennis et al., 2023; Keleher et al., 2022) compared to other MRI modalities (e.g., diffusion MRI) which therefore results in more comparable data collected across sites. The goal of AIMS-TBI is to generate algorithms that can accurately detect and segment 3D lesions, defined as structural damage visible on T1-w MRI due to TBI that may include contusions, hemorrhage, hematoma, encephalomalacia, gliosis, white matter lesions, and surgical drainage tracts.

The inaugural AIMS-TBI Challenge was held at the 2024 MICCAI conference. The final AIMS-TBI 2024 dataset comprised a total of 764 images, including 388 images for training, 101 for validation, and 275 for testing. In the validation phase of the challenge, 12 submissions were uploaded, with 5 teams submitting final models in the test stage. The best performing model achieved an average Dice score of 0.61. This result represented a successful first challenge, yet also highlighted substantial room for improvement. This year's challenge boasts a larger training dataset to enable more accurate lesion segmentation. Precise lesion segmentation is required for advanced image processing and analyses (such as parcellation, functional connectivity analyses, connectomics, and fixel-based analysis) which hold potential for improving prediction of patient outcomes.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

traumatic brain injury, lesion, MRI, segmentation, TBI, detection

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

There are existing challenges focused on multiple other types of lesions - stroke, tumor, etc - but none of these are focused on traumatic brain injury which can have very different neuropathology. We ran the inaugural AIMS-TBI challenge last year and it was a success, we aim to continue and expand it here.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

N/A

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

Based on the number of teams who have participated in related challenges (BraTS - 30, ATLAS - 14, ISLES - 110), we estimate that at least 10 teams will participate.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Yes, in addition to the publications submitted as part of the challenge, we will coordinate a publication after the conclusion of the challenge with members from the 3 top-performing teams.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

Our challenge will be hosted on the Grand Challenge platform. All data will be available through the Challenge platform and/or , and we will use the platform for validation and testing. Projectors will be needed during the challenge, and possibly microphones/speakers depending on the size of the room.

TASK 1: Automated MRI lesion segmentation using T1-weighted MRI scans in moderate-severe TBI

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Detect and segment lesions in T1-weighted MRI data from moderate-severe traumatic brain injury.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

T1-weighted MRI, TBI, traumatic brain injury, lesion, segmentation, detection

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Emily Dennis - University of Utah

Nick Tustison - University of Virginia

Evelyn Deutscher - Deakin University

Elisabeth Wilde - University of Utah

Matthew Pease - Indiana University

Spyridon Bakas - Indiana University

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Emily Dennis - emily.dennis@hsc.utah.edu

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org (Type 2)

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

Grand challenge website has not yet been updated, but here is the link from last year:

<https://aims-tbi.grand-challenge.org/> Additionally, further information and example evaluation scripts can be found here: <https://github.com/adionicas/AIMS-TBI-challenge>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Participants are allowed to use additional data from publicly available datasets and their own institutions, for further complementing the data, but if they do so, they MUST also discuss the potential difference in their results after using only the provided data, since our intention is to solve the particular problem, but also to provide a fair comparison among the participating methods.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but organizers and their immediate groups cannot be 1) eligible for awards, 2) announced as the winners of the challenge, or 3) included in the announced formal rankings. They will however be evaluated and if they are within the top-ranked ones they will be honorarily mentioned to contribute back to the community. Since organizing institutions are large, other employees from other labs/departments that are not associated with the challenge may participate and should be eligible for awards and to be listed in the official leaderboard.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top 3 performing teams will receive a cash prize - \$500 USD for first place, \$250 for second place, \$100 for third place.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Algorithm performance will be posted on the challenge website during the validation phase and updated with each submission. Final performance will be announced at the MICCAI in-person challenge event and the top 3 teams will be listed on the challenge website at this time.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

We are coordinating with the BraTS organizers for joint proceedings allowing our participants to publish their methods in the associated LNCS post-conference proceedings.

Participating teams will be asked to submit a 6-8 page paper on their algorithms and results after the validation phase, due Aug 15 2025, as part of the challenge. The top three teams will be invited to work with the challenge organizers on a challenge paper to be submitted to a medical imaging journal after the conclusion of the challenge. Teams may publish any additional papers after submission of the challenge paper.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Algorithm container submission (type 2) on Grand Challenge.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

We plan to release a validation subset 6 weeks after the release of the training data. The ground truth data for the validation set will not be released, but multiple submissions will be allowed for groups to fine tune their algorithms prior to the final test.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
 - the registration date/period
 - the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
 - the submission date(s)
 - associated workshop days (if any)
 - the release date(s) of the results
- April 1: Training data will be released when the challenge website opens
 - May 15: Validation data will be released
 - June 30: Validation phase closes
 - July 1: Final model submission opens

- August 15: Deadline for challenge papers
- Sept 23/27: Final results announced during the MICCAI 2025 meeting

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

University of Utah IRB has acknowledged the ENIGMA projects as not human subjects due to data de-identification. The University of Utah has DUAs/MTAs/CRADAs/SCCs in place with each site that has contributed data. Data will be further anonymized with the following steps:

- MRI data will be defaced using pydeface with any subject or site data stripped from the metadata
- Subject IDs will be recoded with the key securely held at the University of Utah
- Data will be pooled across sites with no way to re-identify site
- The only demographic data provided along with the MRI data will be age (rounded to the nearest year) and time since injury (in weeks)

With these steps, we are confident that subject/site re-identification will be impossible. Participating challenge teams will need to complete a DUA with the University of Utah prior to receiving access to the data.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

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Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The script for evaluating results from 2024 can be found here: <https://github.com/adionicas/AIMS-TBI-challenge>
We will make some edits for 2025 including new changes such as cluster threshold.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participating teams will be required to submit their code as a container (preferably Singularity) through the challenge website. These will be kept private until the final test, when the top-performing algorithm will be

published.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The National Institutes of Health funds this work.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval

- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation, Detection

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/object(s) from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort would be patients who have sustained a moderate-severe TBI who have T1-weighted MRI data.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort includes subjects from the ENIGMA Pediatric mTBI and ENIGMA Adult mTBI working groups who have T1-weighted MRI data that has been shared with the University of Utah. These two groups are separate for primary analyses of the effect of TBI on brain structure and function to enable careful consideration of developmental concerns, but for the purposes of this challenge they are combined. The data that is included spans ages 5-85 and is 64% male, matching epidemiological trends in TBI. The sample is enriched for adolescents, also reflecting epidemiological trends.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

T1-weighted MRI

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Scanner manufacturer

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Patient age, sex/gender, time since injury

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Brain MRI scan

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

3D lesions in the brain, defined as structural damage visible on T1-w MRI due to TBI that may include contusions, hemorrhage, hematoma, encephalomalacia, gliosis, white matter lesions, and surgical drainage tracts.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Feasibility, Consistency, Precision, Reliability, Sensitivity, Specificity, Usability

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

T1-weighted MRI data from multiple MRI scanner manufacturers (GE, Siemens, Philips)

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Data acquisition includes T1-weighted MRI data acquired on 1.5T and 3T scanners. The vast majority will have 1 mm isotropic voxel sizes, but some sites will vary within standard parameter ranges.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Baylor College of Medicine, University of California Los Angeles, Pennsylvania State University, Kennedy Krieger Institute, Loma Linda University, Nationwide Children's Hospital, Murdoch Children's Research Institute, Deakin University, University of Texas Houston, Kessler Foundation, VA Palo Alto, and the University of Oslo.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Image acquisition was performed by trained health professionals/radiologists at each respective institution.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case refers to one T1w MRI scan from a particular patient. Across the whole dataset, 510 patients had T1-w scans at a single time point, 296 patients had T1-w scans at 2 time points, 8 patients had T1-w scans at 3 time points, and 2 patients had T1-w scans at 4 time points. All longitudinal scans from the same patient have been included within the same training or test set, so as to avoid data leakage. Each of these individual longitudinal scans is considered to be its own "case" as the presentation of lesions can vary across time points. The ground-truth (binary lesion masks) will be provided for the training cases only.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

A total of 875 T1-weighted MRI datasets are split into 500 training (57%), 100 validation (11%), and 275 test cases (32%). Data will come from 13 different sites, with approximately the same distribution of training, validation, and test data randomly selected across sites. All cases in the test set are different from those in the training or validation sets.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

All of the test data is new, unseen data from last year. For future years and to benchmark performance we will maintain the integrity of the current test data. There are 275 datasets in the test phase - 101 subjects have longitudinal data and 73 have a single time point. Longitudinal data is not split between training/validation and test data. 100 datasets will be in the validation phase - this is a smaller proportion as it is primarily used for teams to test the evaluation scripts on their data. 500 training datasets are provided, a relatively large number, to enable creation of a reliable and generalizable model.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The final test set will represent a real-world distribution. Given the heterogeneity present within msTBI MRI data, it is important that successful segmentation algorithms can perform accurately within various datasets.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

The final test has been created to mirror a real-world distribution capturing variances in lesion heterogeneity, whilst also considering the balance of class distribution across training, validation, and testing environments. This strategy aims to create a realistic training and testing environment to develop algorithms capable of identifying heterogeneous lesion types present in real world ms-TBI research data sets. We have ensured that the training and test sets have similar distributions with regard to age, sex, time since injury, and scan manufacturer.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Lesion identification was performed in a four step process beginning with initial automated segmentation, followed by manual review and edits.

Initial automated segmentation:

A vanilla u-net was trained on the ATLAS v2.0 dataset using the ANTsPy/ANTsPyNet packages. Training scripts are available (<https://github.com/ntustison/ANTsXNetTraining/blob/main/Lesions/>). Note that this is not a participating algorithm but contains illustrations of certain approaches/tools that might be useful to the participants including:

- Preprocessing (e.g., bias field correction, denoising, normalization to a template, brain extraction).
- Data augmentation (e.g., simulated bias field, added noise, histogram intensity warping, random spatial transformations).

All these Python-based and R-based tools, including the lesion segmentation algorithm, are listed and demonstrated, complete with data, at <http://www.tinyurl.com/antsxtutorial>.

It is worth noting that although the initial automated algorithm was useful in identifying large lesions (reflecting the nature of stroke data) substantial manual edits were required and thorough review of all other brain regions to ensure that no smaller lesions were missed.

Manual review and edits:

Staff at the University of Utah served as primary raters and were trained under the same protocol and completed segmentations on the same training data. Training data were reviewed by experts (ED and ED) and staff were approved to proceed to real data once they achieved a DSC of 0.6.

One primary rater reviewed the initial automated lesion segmentation result and performed manual edits

A second rater reviewed the edited mask created by the first rater and provided additional edits if necessary

A third and final expert rater reviewed the lesion segmentation, provided minor edits if necessary, and approved the segmentations for inclusion in the challenge dataset (any minor edits were communicated back to the primary raters to improve their following segmentations)

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

As outlined in the abstract, annotators were instructed to outline any regions of visible structural damage. This included contusions, hemorrhage, hematoma, encephalomalacia, gliosis, white matter lesions and surgical drainage tracts. All annotations were performed using ITK snap (Paul A. Yushkevich, Joseph Piven, Heather Cody Hazlett, Rachel Gimpel Smith, Sean Ho, James C. Gee, and Guido Gerig. User-guided 3D active contour segmentation of anatomical structures: Significantly improved efficiency and reliability. Neuroimage 2006 Jul 1;31(3):1116-28.).

Training materials and instructions are summarized here:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1LPoeCDBzCP_vfVOUoIPciCpHP8QdM1Gy

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Manual annotation by 7 primary and 5 expert annotators. Primary annotators were staff at the University of Utah. Expert raters were Emily Dennis, Evelyn Deutscher, Karen Caeyenberghs, Hannah Lindsey, and Elisabeth Wilde.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The annotations were created in a sequential process, after receiving the initial annotator's mask, the second annotator either approved it, or made edits, before sending it to the final expert who again either approved the mask, or made edits prior to approving it.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The only pre-processing will be defacing using pydeface to protect subject privacy. The goal is for the resulting algorithms to be able to handle data from various sources, so no other preprocessing has been done.

Pre-processing steps that may need to be addressed include harmonisation of image parameters including dimensions and voxel sizes and bias correction of image intensity ranges.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter- and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter- and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

It is inherent in manual image annotation that sources of human error will be present. We attempted to minimise this error in two main ways, firstly by providing the same extensive training to all annotators with several training and feedback rounds prior to beginning lesion editing. Subsequently, by ensuring each image was reviewed by two trained annotators followed by review and approval by an expert annotator. Given detailed knowledge of this dataset, it is likely that the primary sources of error may come from slight inaccuracies in the boundaries of lesions identified. As each image was passed through 3 separate reviews, we anticipate the occurrence of missed lesions to be minimal, but still possible. Once this dataset is complete, we plan to implement a quantitative analysis of the error present among annotations, and build a gold-standard subset of annotations following protocols currently being developed by other successful and long-running challenges (BraTS Lighthouse challenge 2025). This work lies outside the scope of this challenge in its second year.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if

any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

For Segmentation:

- Dice similarity coefficient - DSC (voxelwise) = $2TP / (2TP + FN + FP)$
- Absolute volume difference - AVD (voxelwise) = volume annotated - volume rater

For segmentation metrics, TP = True Positive (a voxel correctly identified in the predicted mask, overlapping with the reference mask), FN = False Negative (a voxel in the reference

For Detection:

A lesion is defined as a connected cluster of voxels.

- Absolute lesion count difference - Count (lesion-wise) = Total predicted - total rater
- Detection rate - Detection (lesion-wise) = $2TP_{lesion} / (2TP_{lesion} + FN_{lesion} + FP_{lesion})$

Where:

TP_{lesion} = true positive lesion (a lesion will be considered a TP if the predicted mask overlaps with at least 10% of the reference mask),

FN_{lesion} = false negative lesion (a lesion will be considered a FN if the reference mask contains less than 10% overlap with a predicted mask),

FP_{lesion} = false positive lesion (a predicted lesion will be considered a FP if it does not overlap with at least 10% of a reference mask).

To determine the percent overlap for lesion detection we will use the common Intercept over Union (IoU) approach. Given that ms-TBI lesions can vary dramatically in size and exhibit complex boundaries, it is reasonable to suggest that more lenient thresholds compared to IoU 0.3 - 0.5 (common in biomedical imaging tasks) could be justified (Reinke et al., 2024). To prioritise sensitivity, we have chosen a threshold of IoU 0.1 meaning a lesion will be identified as a True Positive only if it overlaps with 10% of the reference mask, this is a threshold in line with others utilised in MICCAI challenges (i.e., Artificial Intelligence and Radiologists in Prostate Cancer Detection on MRI (PIC-CAI) challenge [Saha et al., 2024] and the Pancreatic Cancer Diagnosis - Radiologists Meet AI (PANORAMA) challenge [Alves et al., 2024]). If a predicted mask overlaps with less than 10% it will be disregarded as a false positive.

A. Saha, J. S. Bosma, J. J. Twilt, B. van Ginneken, A. Bjartell, A. R. Padhani, D. Bonekamp, G. Villeirs, G. Salomon, G. Giannarini, J. Kalpathy-Cramer, J. Barentsz, K. H. Maier-Hein, M. Rusu, O. Rouvière, R. van den Bergh, V. Panebianco, V. Kasivisvanathan, N. A. Obuchowski, D. Yakar, M. Elschot, J. Veltman, J. J. Fütterer, M. de Rooij, H. Huisman, and the PI-CAI consortium. "Artificial Intelligence and Radiologists in Prostate Cancer Detection on MRI (PI-CAI): An International, Paired, Non-Inferiority, Confirmatory Study". *The Lancet Oncology* 2024; 25(7): 879-887.

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Reinke, A., Tizabi, M. D., Baumgartner, M., Eisenmann, M., Heckmann-Nötzel, D., Kavur, A. E., ... & Maier-Hein, L. (2024). Understanding metric-related pitfalls in image analysis validation. *Nature methods*, 21(2), 182-194.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The metrics chosen were selected to assess both detection accuracy and segmentation accuracy, with Dice widely used in medical segmentation challenges and tasks. Due to the large heterogeneity in patient presentations and injuries in ms-TBI, identifying when there is not a lesion present is also important, not only accurate segmentation of lesions that are present. The voxelwise metrics provide information about segmentation accuracy while the lesion-wise metrics reflect detection accuracy.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

We will compute average DSC, AVD, Count, and Detection across cases. The groups will receive a rank of 1 through N (number of teams participating) for each of the four metrics with rank 1 for DSC and detection given to the team with the highest values and rank 1 for AVD and count given to the team with the lowest values. These four ranks will be summed and the team with the smallest sum will rank first and on down.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For instances where submitted algorithms fail to produce a mask/label for a specific test case, the metrics for that test case will be set to their worst possible value (e.g., 0 for the DSC).

As an addition to this year's challenge we will include an investigation of model performance using the same four metrics, applied to separate groups of cases (i.e., those with lesions present, and those without). This separate calculation will not be included in the rankings as outlined above, but is provided to enhance our understanding of how the models are performing in cases where no lesion masks exist.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The goal is to identify the algorithm that achieves the best performance over both lesion detection and segmentation tasks. The metrics selected have been chosen to address both of these tasks, utilising metrics and ranking schemes that have been employed in previous medical imaging segmentation challenges (Ischemic Stroke Lesion Segmentation challenge [ISLES] <https://zenodo.org/records/10991145>)

de la Rosa, E., Kirschke, J. S., Wiestler, B., Wiest, R., Reyes, M., Su, R., Wegener, S., & Menze, B. (2024). Ischemic Stroke Lesion Segmentation Challenge 2024. 27th International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention (MICCAI 2024). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10991145>

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,

- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

None

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

None

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

None

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

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Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A